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Water Vapor Corrosion Behavior and Failure Mechanism of Plasma Sprayed Mullite/Lu₂Si₂O₇-Lu₂SiO₅ Coatings

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- 3 **Results and Discussions**
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1 Research Background and Significance

Aero Engine Development Trend

- High thrust-weight ratio
- Higher turbine inlet temperature
- Low fuel consumption
- Long service life

1 Research Background and Significance

MATERIALS SCIENCE

The Hotter the Engine, the Better

John H. Perepezko

Alloys based on molybdenum or niobium may allow the high-temperature components of jet engines to run hotter and more efficiently.

世界上最大商用航空发动机GE9X采用CMC制备的燃烧室和涡轮已开始地面测试

1 Research Background and Significance

In dry air: $\text{Si(s)} + \text{O}_2(\text{g}) \rightarrow \text{SiO}_2(\text{s})$

In water vapor containing environment:
 $\text{SiO}_2(\text{s}) + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g}) \rightarrow \text{Si}(\text{OH})_4(\text{g})$

Ceramics recession at high temperature due to water vapor

These corrosion problems can be alleviated by EBCs, preventing Si-based ceramic materials from reacting with water vapor

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2.1 Materials

The mullite ($3Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2$) powder (18–58 μm), lutetium silicate composite powder ($m LuDS / m LuMS = 6:4$, 50–125 μm)

2.2 Deposition parameters for APS mullite/LuDS-LuMS layers

APS Layer	Voltage (V)	Arc current (A)	Ar (slm)	H ₂ (slm)	Distance (mm)	Carrier Ar (slm)
LuDS-LuMS	64	548	50	1.0	120	15
Mullite	68	493	45	1,0	120	15

2 Materials and Experimental

2.2 water vapor corrosion setup and experimental methodology

experimental methodology:

- 1450°C 95% H₂O-5% air
- The flow velocity of water vapor was 0.54 m/s
- For each thermal cycling
- corrosion test, the samples were firstly heated for 2.5 h at 1450 °C, cooled down to the room temperature within 2 min by compressed air jet.
- Analyses are made with X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to understand how the surface changes after exposure
- An electronic balance with a sensitivity of ± 0.1 mg was used to quantify the weight change of the coated samples before and after thermal cycling corrosion test

Experimental setup:

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3 Results and Discussions

X-ray diffraction:

- Fig.2. XRD patterns for the feedstock powders of mullite and LuDS-LuMS and the corresponding as-sprayed coatings by APS.

- Fig.3. The rietveld refinement of experimental XRD data of mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating surface after exposure to water vapor at 1450 °C for different hours. (a) 0 h; (b) 100 h; (c) 150 h.

3 Results and Discussions

- Phase composition deduced from Rietveld refinement of the XRD patterns for LuDS-LuMS coating surface after exposure to water vapor at 1450 °C for different hours (a) 0 h; (b)100 h; (c) 150 h, respectively.

Sample	Phase composition (wt %)				
	Lu ₂ SiO ₅	Lu ₂ Si ₂ O ₇	Lu ₃ Al ₅ O ₁₂	Al ₂ SiO ₅	Amorphous
a	22.83	42.90	0	0	34.27
b	29.84	62.20	5.65	0	2.31
c	22.93	65.13	9.65	1.02	1.27

Data collection: Cu ($K\alpha_1/\alpha_2$); 2θ range: 10–60 °; Step width: 0.02 °; Time per steps: 1 s.

3 Results and Discussions

Exposure to water vapor:

- Fig.4. Macrographs of SiC Substrate coated with mullite/LuDS–LuMS coating (a) before and (b) after 150 h corrosion.

- Fig.5. Variation in weight gain with the steam cycling cycles and steam cycling time.

Scanning electron microscopy

- Fig.6. SEM microstructures on (a-b) the surface and (b-d) the cross-section of the as-sprayed (a,c) mullite and (b,d) mullite/LuDS -LuMS coatings deposited on SiC substrate.
- The fully melted and partly melted regions as well as some small pores are clearly observed on the coating surface.
- The crosssection microstructure of the mullite coating mainly includes circular or elliptical fine pores, which are originated from the entrapment of the gas with liquid droplets.
- The mullite layer and the LuDS-LuMS layer are clearly seen and well distributed on the SiC substrate. It is hard to observe vertical and horizontal cracks and interfacial pores between the mullite layer and the LuDS-LuMS layer, implying good chemical compatibility between the two ceramic layers

3 Results and Discussions

Scanning electron microscopy

- Fig.7. (a) Microstructure and (d) EDS-line analysis on the cross-section of porous SiC with mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating after 150 h water vapor corrosion test, and (b-c) high magnification SEM images of region (A) and (B) marked in Figure (a), respectively.
- Comparing Fig. 7(a) with Fig. 6(c-d), we can see that the size of the interfacial pores between the mullite and SiC substrates are progressively increased, suggesting oxidation of the SiC substrate surface.
- Fig. 7(d) shows the EDS-line spectra on the cross section of mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating after 150 h of corrosion test. Based on the EDS analysis, the inter-diffusion of atoms between the mullite and LuDS-LuMS layers took place during the heating process.

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4 Conclusions

- LuDS–LuMS powders have been synthesized and new bi-layer mullite/LuDS–LuMS EBCs have been successfully fabricated on the SiC substrate by APS.
- The coating, with a good interfacial bonding and corrosion resistance, can endure 150 h steam cycling test (60 cycles) at 1450°C.
- The coating maintain weight gain and average weight gain rate is 1.12×10^{-1} mg/cm² h.
- The appearance of through and horizontal cracks are attributed to the accumulation of thermal mismatch stress and aging stress. The CTE mismatch between the coating and the substrate as well as between the two ceramic layers produces thermal mismatch stress. The chemical reaction induce the sintering of LuDS-LuMS layer, the amorphous-crystalline phase transformation and the transformation between LuDS and LuMS result in the aging stress.
- With the accumulation of thermal mismatch stress and aging stress, the through and horizontal cracks have appeared in the coating, leading to the coating failure.

THANK YOU

